

A Post Humanist Understanding of Marginalized Feminism in Humans in The Loop

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Abstract:

The aim of this research paper is to examine and understand the marginalization of feminism especially Adivasi woman in the acclaimed Netflix film titled Humans in the Loop(2024) directed by Aranya Sahay through the critical lens of Post humanism. Post humanism is a current literary theory making waves in the field of literary criticism. Post humanism emerges out of humanism that posits humans at the centre of everything. From the age of Renaissance to Enlightenment, humanism projected the limitless boundaries of human mind and the ability to question and rationalizes everything. Post humanism looks at these very boundaries and blurring of boundaries through machines, cyborgs, cybernetics and most important artificial intelligence or AI. In the world of 'post human times' (Rosi Bradiotti), we are challenged by unmitigated climate disorder, climate change, cloning, mass extinction of species caused by human centered approach and centrality. Post human thought postulates a concept and world that is not different from machines and non human world and that we are perhaps more like others than ourselves. As a human, we are constantly challenged by dominant and subversive power structures that are antithetical to humanism. With the advent of AI and its reach on every aspect of human kind, society and institutions, the boundary between human and non-human and post human is increasingly blurred.

Aranya Sahay's Humans in the Loop is a remarkable story of a marginalized indigenous Adivasi woman Nehma who forms the face of the invisible labour force feeding AI captcha images in a mechanical manner. On the one hand Nehma faces the bubble of machine doing routine work and on the other attempts to subvert patriarchy and dominant power structures to support her family after her separation from her partner. Through post humanist lens, the film is multilayered to expose the vulgar differences existing in our society.

Keywords: AI, Post humanism, feminism, Humans in the Loop

Introduction:

As the film *Humans in the Loop* opens, the viewer finds a young Nehma grazing the ground with her eyes locked with the open blue sky. Then she locks her eye with the porcupine. The porcupine is at a distance from her both are aware of their personal space and territory and do not impinge upon each other. Both respect each other's spaces filled with coexistence and mutual understanding. This human nature bond and connection stays throughout the film and appears at regular intervals in the film. Cut to the next scene, the film captures a 'data labelling' center where women employees have to read, edit and save captcha images for a client albeit an international one. The women seem

comfortable and compatible with the machines and the only sound is of the clicking of the mouse on the images. Nehma has to appear for a test and identify all the images correctly. During the test, she comes across images of porcupine and she pauses, mesmerized by the porcupine of her childhood. Nehma is caught in a time loop and unaware of the time comes to her senses as the supervisor gives the warning sign for the completion of test within time schedule. As a result, Nehma is unable to complete the test and does not qualify. Her friend requests the supervisor to consider Nehma despite the unsuccessful attempt as she needs the job to safeguard her family. The film navigates different tropes regarding women, their roles, parent child

relationship and most importantly Nehma's uneasy relationship with AI and computing.

Humans in the Loop challenges the notion of posthumanism as a critical discourse because in the film, humans are pitted against machines and AI that are considered to be more intelligent than humans. Post humanism as a political and philosophical discourse has been in academic domains since the 1990's but is more discussed now amid the rise and increased dependency on machines, AI and technology. The prefix 'post' attached to humanism suggests after or beyond humanism is suspect. Posthumanism emerged out of humanism that placed humans at the supremacy and center of everything and everyone in the ecosystem. Beginning from Renaissance, humanism signified a new turn and direction towards knowledge and imparting of knowledge. Scientists, painters, poets and artists all contributed towards the development of humanism so much so that Shakespeare wrote in Hamlet, "What a piece of work man is." Humanism is a Western philosophical concept that can also be called as anthropocentric and androcentric that put down the importance of the non human and other. In fact, post humanism can be called as the 'de-centering' of the human arguing for transhumanism and antihumanism. The question what is to be human is being challenged by the posthumanists who perceive the role of humans trying to adjust and live with technology, cyborgs and AI.

Ihab Hassan, a literary theorist described the advent of posthumanist tradition to revive the internal feelings and consciousness of a human, "The human form, including human desire and all its external representations, may change radically and thus must be re-visioned. We must understand that five hundred years of humanism may end, as humanism transforms itself into something we must helplessly call Posthumanism." Posthumanism is placed at the intersection of human, non human and technological realms gaining importance over ecological consciousness and questioning the role of humanity in creating and shaping Earth. In the contemporary scenario, media technology and social

media are important to experience what the real human is. Cloning came as a breakthrough in technology where a being could be replicated in substitutes raising the ethical dilemma of the living. Similarly, media technologies like VR (Virtual Reality), AR (Augmented Reality), AI (Artificial Intelligence) are tools with which we interact and mix. As we use these tools more often, the world of reality and virtual is blurred in the post human condition. Posthumanism stresses moving beyond a human focused perspective to a broad point of view that includes technology, artificial intelligence and other entities beyond humans. It attempts to address how technology impacts identity consciousness and the physical boundaries of humans.

Posthumanism as a critical discourse has found a lot of fandom in popular culture especially in films such as *Blade Runner*, video game series *Deus Ex*, *The Matrix*. As a literary discourse, early instances of posthumanism can be observed in the short story, "The Man that was Used Up" by Edgar Allan Poe as early as 1843 followed by Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein*.

Coming back to *Humans in the Loop*, Nehma in the film is a single mother picking up the threads of her life after her separation from her partner struggling to find a semblance of normalcy with her twelve-year-old daughter Dhaanu and toddler son Guntu. Nehma leaves the urban Ranchi and comes to live in her native rural surroundings. The film alternates between the present day Nehma and young childhood in harmony with natural surroundings. The job as a data labeler is the lifeline for Nehma as she can prove her ability to support her children as a single mother. Nehma slowly regains a balance between her work and family life. But she is unable to gain her daughter's empathy post separation. Dhaanu is always in touch and communication with her father over the phone. She does not like the school in the village where the girls watch her curiously. But one student, Malti befriends her and slowly Dhaanu comes out of her shell.

On the work front, Nehma spends her time editing images for captcha that are stored in pen drive to be scrutinized by her supervisor. Every week the women employees are given new themes to search for images, edit and feed into the pen drive. One such assignment comes in the form of ‘pests.’ They are taught by their supervisor on how to search for images on pests and label them accordingly through presentation. Nehma does not relate to one image of pest that is of a worm nibbling on leaf. As a data labeler, Nehma becomes sensitive to bias against many aspects such as her identity, feminism, indigenous identity as perceived through western gaze. Nehma does not approve of these biases but is silenced by her supervisor and focus on her work. In one such episode, Nehma is performing AI Art Generator and stumbles upon trying to edit authentic images of woman. On a whim, Nehma starts to type different keywords such as ‘Adivasi woman’, ‘tribal Indian woman’, and she is assaulted with images not related to the original. She chances upon her daughter’s smart phones with beautiful images of the hamlet, people and their world in their authenticity and accuracy. Nehma selects these pictures and labels them according to her understanding and not the ‘captcha.’ She then takes it to her supervisor and convinces her that AI is like a child...whatever we feed, it takes that. Nehma further reiterates that the worm nibbling on a leaf is not a pest as it consumes and eats only the rotten part of the leaf and not the whole leaf. “. . . Right now, AI is like a child, still learning. If its algorithms are made more representative, inclusive of the diversity of humanity, AI could serve us still better.” (Bhura)

Humans in the Loop is a multilayered film and comments in the credits about the impact of AI on society. The film also revolves around the search for roots especially for both Nehma and Dhaanu. For Nehma, it is a comeback to where she belonged. But for Dhaanu, it becomes reconciliation with her mother. Dhaanu is initially shown as recalcitrant and withdrawn but in love with her younger brother. Once she attempts to run away from home with her

younger brother to Ranchi to her father. Guided by Google Maps, she follows the instruction only to realize that there is no way out. In the evening, she is unable to trace the route to highway and is resting in the forest. The porcupine appears again and comes closer to the toddler Guntu but doesn’t harm him. Dhaanu finds it odd to be accosted by the animal. As she is walking, she is searched by her mother and brought back safely to her home. Later Dhaanu is informed that her mother Nehma and the porcupine shared a very close bond with each other and were popular in the village and community. Probably, the porcupine must have come thinking about Nehma.

Aim and Objective of Study:

This paper attempts to look at posthumanist angle and perspective in the film *Humans in the Loop* and how the film challenges the notion of the supremacy of AI over every aspect of our lives—personal and public through the protagonist Nehma.

Methodology:

The paper tries to understand the critical discourse of posthumanism and a close reading of the film. Humanism was largely seen as male and imperial excluded many humans such as women, queer, immigrants, minorities as ‘Other.’ The film makes a case for posthumanist discourse in popular culture especially in cinema to look at marginalized feminism with technology through the indigenous female gaze. Artificial intelligence in the film also appears to be the subject of the supremacy of the Western imperial thought as the images data labeled are to appeal and approve the Western audience that is largely homogenous. The film also attempts to give Nehma, the protagonist autonomy and freedom in exercising her right in choosing the images in an ethical manner for greater visibility.

Conclusion:

The film leaves the audience to think about the invisible work of marginalized rural women of India, insisting on feeding ethical data to AI and not

to demonize it. The film raises ethical questions of identity, divergent views of identity and non conformative role of identity formation. Nehma appropriates the data labeling platform by making it less technological through original photographs of Adivasi woman instead of AI powered photographs. The posthumanist turn in the film occurs when Nehma is satisfied with the authenticity of the images that she uploads on the computer and the appropriation of technology and working along with it not against it and certainly not by it. The porcupine acts as the symbol of resistance especially by asserting and affirming the role of indigenous communities in knowledge creation, sharing and transfer. “At its heart, *Humans in the Loop* becomes an act of decolonizing imagination. Nehma’s desire to raise AI with Adivasi knowledge highlights how today’s AI systems depend on

Eurocentric datasets that flatten or erase indigenous perspectives.” (Bunkar)

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